

Ethics - guidelines for framing nonhuman animal-based research in an ACI context

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Please note: references in this document to 'animals' should be interpreted as meaning 'non human animals'.

The ACI context is predominantly 'animal-centred'.

I would suggest that you read Mancini's paper 'Towards an Animal-Centred Ethics for Animal-Computer Interaction' (I've attached this as a PDF) [1].

You may find it useful to think about the: "reframing of animal research from an animal-centred perspective" [1].

Also, I would suggest bearing in mind my own comment that, "our commitment to non-human animals: build only what they want or need" [2].

How do you think that your work relates to this last statement?

If this is a welfare-focused technology, perhaps there needs to be discussion about how this is improving the wellbeing of the studied animals, irrespective of their intended ultimate use (for example: death in the case of meat animals, or potentially shortened lifespan and stress in the case of dairy cows).

You need to demonstrate your understanding that ACI studies of practices with negative outcomes for animals may be controversial to some in an animal-centred community. This is the case even where the ACI researcher is not directly involved in the negative outcome (for example: it happens after the study), or it is considered 'socially accepted practice'.

Please explain why you believe that your research is justifiable (improved welfare etc.).

If you have not yet undertaken your research, consider how you can make the design process animal-centred. For example: how might any technical intervention be perceived by the animal? Is training / habituation required in order to introduce the technology? Have you looked into using the 'voluntary cooperation' / 'protected contact' training techniques, practiced in progressive zoos? Does the animal have an option to withdraw? Is the animal's behaviour modified by your technology (and how did you measure this)?

If your study has already been completed, it may not be possible to retrospectively make this work more animal-centred.

I would suggest demonstrating that you have reflected on these issues and that there is some (brief) discussion of them.

The easiest way to resolve this, might be to include a new short section / subsection, with a title such as: 'ethics, welfare and animal-centred design' (or however you want to phrase it).

Alternatively, you might find ways to reflect on ethical and user-centred design, in the paper sections where it is most appropriate.

A useful set of guidelines (to help you write a new section) might be Mancini's five ethical principles for animal-centred research (see the paper for a full description) [1]:

1. Respecting and caring for every participant without discrimination
2. Garnering participants mediated and contingent consent
3. Doing research that is relevant to participants and consistent with their welfare
4. Avoiding research procedures that may be harmful to participants
5. Assessing research proposals and obtaining expert support (for example: did these studies get ethics committee approval within the authors' institutions? Was an animal behaviour expert consulted?)

References

[1] Clara Mancini, 2017. Towards an Animal-Centred Ethics for Animal-Computer Interaction. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 98, 221-233.
<http://dx.doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2016.04.008>.

[2] Anna Zamansky, Amanda Roshier, Clara Mancini, Emily C. Collins, Carol Hall, Katie Grillaert, Ann Morrison, Steve North, and Hanna Wirman, 2017. A Report on the First International Workshop on Research Methods in Animal-Computer Interaction. In *Proceedings of the Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems (Denver, Colorado, USA 2017)*, ACM, 3052759, 806-815.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/3027063.3052759>.